

Table I. Data Collection and Assessment Criteria

Criteria	Description
Collection	
Data Collection Tool	<i>Publish or Perish</i>
Database	<i>Scopus</i>
Title Word	<i>Islamic green economy, green sukuk, Islamic green finance, Islamic green business, Islamic green market, Islamic sustainable economy, Islamic sustainable development, Islamic bio-economy, Islamic circular economy, dan Islamic green management</i>
Timeline	2013- March 2023
Assessment	
Type	Journal article
Topic	Islamic green economy and other related topics
Appraisal Website	https://www.scimagojr.com/ , https://www.scopus.com/
Quartile	Q1-Q4

Table II. Publishers and Journals that Publish Research Related to Islamic Green Economy

Publisher	Journal	Amount
American-Eurasian Network for Scientific Information Publications	Advances in Environmental Biology	1
Brill	Arab Law Quarterly	2
	Worldviews	1
Cambridge University Press	Review of Middle East Studies	1
Dublin Institute of Technology	International Journal of Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage	1
Elsevier	Chaos, Solitons & Fractals	1
	Energy Economics	1
	Global Finance Journal	1
	Journal of Cleaner Production	3
	Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions, and Money	1
	Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and Its Applications	1
	Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	1
EconJournals	International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy	3
Emerald Publishing	Humanomics	3
	International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management	1
	International Journal of Managerial Finance	1
	International Journal of Manpower	1
	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	1
	Journal of Islamic Marketing	4
	Qualitative Research in Financial Market	1
	Sustainability Accounting, Management, and Policy Journal	1
Frontiers Media S.A.	Frontiers in Psychology	1
Growing Science	Management Science Letters	1
	Uncertain Supply Chain Management	1
IAEME Publication	International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology	1
Inderscience Publishers	International Journal of Environment and Sustainable Development	1
	International Journal of Green Economics	1
Institut Pengurusan Penyelidikan (RMI), Universiti Teknologi MARA	Journal of Mechanical Engineering	1
International Islamic University Malaysia	Al-Shajarah: Journal of the International Institute of Islamic Thought and Civilization	1
King Abdulaziz University Scientific Publishing Center	Journal of King Abdulaziz University Islamic Economics	1
Kolej Universiti Islam Sultan Azlan	Global Journal Al-Thaqafah	1

Shah		
Maulana Malik Ibrahim State Islamic University of Malang	Journal of Islamic Architecture	1
Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute	Administrative Sciences	1
	Energies	1
	Sustainability	2
Sage Publication	Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space	1
Society for Alliance, Fidelity, and Advancement	International Journal of Business and Management Science	1
Springer	Environment, Development, and Sustainability	1
	Journal of Religion and Health	1
STAIN Kudus	Qudus International Journal of Islamic Studies	1
Statistical Economic and Social Research and Training Centre for Islamic Countries	Journal of Economic Cooperation and Development	1
Taylor & Francis	Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment	1
	Social and Environmental Accountability Journal	1
University of Management and Technology	Journal of Islamic Thought and Civilization	1
Wiley-Blackwell	Sustainable Development	1
World Scientific	Singapore Economic Review	1

Table III. Future Research Suggestion regarding Islamic Green Economy

Themes	Future Research Suggestion
Green Concept & Environmental Concern	1. Proposing a framework to enhance the environmental awareness of Muslims in Saudi Arabia and Brunei Darussalam.
Green Banking	2. Examining the factors that drive the implementation of green banking in Bangladesh. Examining the impact of green banking on: 3. Performance, 4. Efficiency, 5. Financing, 6. Rentability, 7. Market structure, 8. Market share, of Islamic banking in Bangladesh. Examining the impact of green banking on: 9. Profitability, 10. Performance, 11. Efficiency, 12. Financing, 13. Rentability, 14. Market structure, 15. Market share, of Islamic banking in Iran. Examining the impact of green banking on: 16. Profitability 17. Efficiency 18. Financing, 19. Rentability, 20. Market structure, 21. Market share, of Islamic banking in Malaysia.
Green Sukuk	22. Proposing green sukuk criteria that are acceptable in many countries, effective, and efficient. 23. Proposing efforts to unify green sukuk policies in Saudi Arabia
Green Financial Market	24. Reviewing green sukuk & green bond instruments as safe haven features.
Green Framework & Management	25. Examining the relationship or linkage between green framework & management research and the attitude of managers, practitioners, or policymakers to adopt and implement the proposed design.
Sustainable Development Goals	26. Examining Islamic economics' role in helping achieve other Sustainable Development Goals, especially goals 8, 9, 10, and 12.

- Renewable Energy 27. Examining the relationship and influence of religiosity factors on adopting renewable energy from Islamic countries.
- Green Education 28. Proposing a green Islamic boarding school framework for all Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia.
29. Examining the perceptions of stakeholders (in this case, leaders of Islamic boarding schools and scholars) in Indonesia towards the green Islamic boarding school concept.
- Green Growth Factors 30. Exploring other factors that can stimulate green growth in other Islamic countries.